

The Influence of Learning Discipline and Teacher Teaching Style on The Learning Achievement of Class VIII Students of SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar in The 2023/2024 Academic Year.

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to gain knowledge regarding the influence of learning discipline and teacher teaching styles on the learning achievement of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year. This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive data analysis approach with the testing media used is SPSS 21. The population in this study was 277 people, and the sample used was 163 people. The sample collection technique used was Proportionate Stratified Random sampling. The data collection technique used was a questionnaire. The hypothesis data collection technique uses multiple regression analysis and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The results of this research state that: 1) there is a positive influence of learning achievement on learning discipline. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value of parental income (15.011) > t table value (1.65437). 2) there is a negative and insignificant influence of the teacher's teaching style on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value of social style (-0.725) > t table value (1.65437) which means that this variable is not significant. 3) learning discipline and the teacher's teaching style together influence learning discipline. This result can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value (187.479) > Ftable value (3.05). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.701, which means that 70.1% of the variables are the influence of learning discipline and teacher teaching styles on the learning achievement of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar and 29.9% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research. *Keywords:* Learning Achievement, Learning Discipline, Teacher Teaching Style

INTRODUCTION

Education is important for human survival. Education is an activity carried out by every human being so that they obtain knowledge that can be developed as a preparation to become a qualified and responsible successor to the nation, especially in the development of science and technology. The level of success of an education can be seen from the learning achievements achieved by students. There are many factors that cause the learning achievement of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar to remain low, including a lack of student discipline. Discipline contains the meaning that is manifested in a person's behavior with the aim that all his actions always comply with applicable rules or regulations. Learning discipline is a form of awareness of actions to learn such as discipline in following lessons, accuracy in completing assignments, discipline in taking exams, discipline in adhering to study schedules, discipline in obeying rules and regulations. which has a direct influence on students' methods and techniques in learning, the results of which can be seen from the learning achievements achieved. High learning discipline will increase high achievement, but if students' learning discipline is low, achievement will decrease.

The teacher's teaching style is one factor in increasing student motivation in learning. The teacher's teaching style must be varied and creative, because if the teacher uses various methods in learning activities the teacher can improve student learning achievement. In teaching, teachers must often motivate students in class to be more diligent in going to school, doing the assignments given by the teacher to students and not looking at their friends' assignments.

In connection with the explanation of learning achievement above, the researcher made observations at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar, where the results of observations made by researchers on the learning achievements of students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar showed that learning achievement was still not satisfactory. This can be seen from the semester student report card data

shows that there are several students who do not reach the minimum completion criteria (KKM), namely the class with the most students who do not reach the KKM is class VII-1 with a percentage of 15.62%, class VII-2 where the percentage is 34.37% with a total of 11 students. students, class VII-3 where with a percentage of 28.12% with a total of 9 students, class VII-4 with a percentage of 6.25 with a number of 2 students, class VII-5 with a percentage of 53.12% with a total of 17 students, class VII-6 with a percentage of 9.77% with a total of 3 students, and a total of VII-7 with a presentation of 43.37% with a total of 11, class VII-8 with a percentage of % d43.75 with a total of 14 students and class VII-9 with a presentation of 40.62% with 13 students. This condition is thought to be due to a lack of learning discipline and the teacher's teaching style during the learning process carried out in the classroom. If the grades on a student's report card do not reach the KKM determined by the school, the student's learning achievement will decrease further.

Based on the above phenomenon, the author is interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Learning Discipline and Teacher Teaching Style on the Learning Achievement of Class VIII Students of SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar Academic Year 2023/2024.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Arikunto in Ananda, R., & Hayati, F. (2020) that discipline is a person's obedience in following rules or regulations because it is driven by the awareness that exists in his heart. Learning discipline is a student's obedience in following rules or regulations driven by the awareness that exists in his conscience.

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According to Ahmadi in Ayu, F. (2022). Teaching style is the teacher's behavior, attitudes and actions in carrying out the teaching process. Teaching style is a teacher's style or behavior as a statement of his personality in conveying lesson material to students.

A teacher is someone who teaches other people. From the definitions above, it can be concluded that teaching style is the way a teacher conveys information or knowledge from both the teacher, the delivery of subject matter, the use of media, voice intonation when teaching and changing the teacher's behavior, attitudes and actions in the learning context which aims to overcome boredom

According to Winkel in Lidia Susanti (2019:33) Learning achievement is proof of a student's success and ability to carry out their learning activities according to the amount they have achieved. Rosyid in Lidia Susanti (2019:30) revealed that learning achievement is expressed in the form of symbols, numbers, letters and sentences which can reflect the results that have been achieved by each student in a certain period and it can be said that learning achievement is the result of a learning activity. accompanied by changes achieved by students.

METHODS

This research was conducted at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar Jl Sibolga No.25, kec. South Siantar, Pematang Siantar City, North Sumatra. This research uses a quantitative approach with survey methods. The population of this study were Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. The sampling technique used in this research was proportionate random sampling, so the number of samples used by researchers was 163 people. The data collected in this research is the result of distributing questionnaires through questionnaires and then to determine whether the instrument statement items are suitable to be given, the validity of the instrument is first carried out. The validity test was tested using SPSS 21, the reliability used the Cronbach Alpha formula. The test results that have been tested are then given to the sample. The data analysis technique used to test the research hypothesis is the T test and F test. Before carrying out the t test, the prerequisite tests are first carried out, namely the normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test.

RESULTS

Before testing the hypothesis, prerequisite tests are carried out, namely the normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test. Based on the normality test, it is presented in the following table:

Table 1. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		163
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	2,82833263
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,056
	Positive	,051
	Negative	-.056
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		,719
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,687

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Based on the results of the normality test, it is known that the significance value is $0.687 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the residual value is normally distributed.

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
Disiplin belajar	.561	1.782
Gaya mengajar guru	.561	1.782

The assumption of Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) can be stated that if $VIF > 10$ and Tolerance value < 0.10 then multicollinearity occurs, and if $VIF < 10$ and Tolerance value > 0.10 then multicollinearity does not occur. Based on table 4.9, Tolerance > 0.10 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10 , it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity in the data, and each independent variable is free from correlation between the independent variables.

Table 3. T Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-7,903	3,063		-2,580	,011
X1	,602	,040	,864	15,011	,000
X2	-,063	,087	-,042	-,725	,469

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement

Based on table 4.11, the tcount value for learning discipline (15.011) is greater than ttable (1.65437) and the tcount value for teacher teaching style (-725) is greater than ttable (1.65437). Thus, the independent variable has an effect but is not significant on the dependent variable

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3041,050	2	1520,525	187,479	,000 ^b
Residual	1297,662	160	8,110		
Total	4338,712	162			

a. Dependent Variable: Prestasi Belajar

b. Predictors: (Constant), gaya mengajar guru, disiplin belajar

Based on table 4.12, it is found that the Fcount value (187.479) is greater than the Ftable value (3.05). This indicates that the research results reject H0 and accept H1. Thus, simultaneously the learning discipline and teacher's teaching style influence the student learning achievement variable at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar with a significant level of influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that learning discipline and teacher teaching style simultaneously influence student learning achievement variables at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar as acceptable..

DISCUSSION

In the classical assumption results, the normality test is the main requirement to be able to proceed to the multiple regression test stage with the data having a normal distribution and a significance level > 0.05 . on the variables of learning discipline, teacher teaching style and student learning achievement have a normal distribution between variables with a significant level of $0.200 > 0.05$. and based on Figure 4.2, the p-plot curve can be seen that the distribution of data is on a diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal, so that the values are standardized and follow the assumption of normality.

The results of the multi collinearity test show that the tolerance is > 0.10 , and the variance inflation factor (VIP) is $1.782 < 10$ and the tolerance value is $0.561 > 0.10$, so it can be concluded that the data does not have symptoms of multi collinearity. The results of the heteroscedasticity test in Figure 4.1 show that the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity, and based on table 4.10 it is known that the significant value of learning discipline is (0.7903) and the significant value of teacher style. teaching (0.3063) and learning achievement scores (0.469) can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity because the significance value must be greater than 0.05. Based on table 4.10, it is known that the constant value (a) is 7.903, while the learning discipline value (b) is 0.602 and the value of the teacher's teaching style (2) is 0.063, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = -7.903 + 0.602X_1 + 0.063X_2 + 1297.662$$

The constant of -7.903 means that the consistent value of the learning achievement variable is 7.903. The regression coefficient X_1 is 0.602 and X_2 is 0.063. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variables X_1 and Variable X_2 on Y is positive. The t test results are based on table 4.11. The calculated t value of learning discipline (15.011) is greater than the t table (1.65437). Based on the results obtained, H_1 is rejected and H_0 is accepted for the learning discipline variable. Thus, learning discipline has no effect on learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. and the calculated t value of the teacher's teaching style (-725) is greater than the t table (1.65437). Based on the results obtained, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted for the teacher teaching style variable. Thus, learning discipline partially has no effect on learning achievement, and the teacher's teaching style partially has an effect on learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar.

In particular, the learning discipline variable has a more dominant influence than the teacher's teaching style. This can be seen from learning discipline having the highest score (15.011), meaning that the discipline variable has more influence in improving learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar while the teacher's teaching style does not influence learning achievement. The F test results based on table 4.12 show that the Fcount value (187.479) is greater than the Ftable value (3.05).

This identifies that the research results reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Thus, simultaneously the learning discipline and teaching style of the teacher influence the learning achievement variables of students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. With a significant level of influence. The coefficient of determination R squer value in table 4.13 is known to be 0.701, which means that 70.1% of the variables of learning discipline and teacher teaching style influence the learning achievement of students at

SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar, while 29.9% is the influence of other variables not examined in the research. This

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

There is no positive and significant influence of learning discipline on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of learning discipline (15.011) < t table value (1.65437) which means this variable is not significant. There is a positive and significant influence on students' social patterns on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of the teacher's teaching style is (-725) > t table (1.65437) which means this variable is significant. Parental upbringing and students' social patterns jointly influence learning achievement. This result can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value (187.479) > Ftable value (3.05). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.701, which means that 70.1% of the variables of old learning discipline and teacher teaching styles have an influence on student learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 29.9% is the influence of other variables not examined in the research this.

Recommendation

1. Learning discipline and teacher teaching style have a positive and significant effect on learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. Therefore, to improve student learning achievement, you should pay attention to these two factors so that learning achievement at school increases. Learning discipline, such as time discipline, needs to be paid attention to by teachers, especially during study time. This is very helpful in improving student learning achievement. Apart from time discipline, action discipline is also very helpful in improving student learning achievement. The teacher's teaching style is also very influential in improving student learning achievement in school, with the teacher's teaching style being good and varied and the teacher must pay attention to appearance when teaching so that students are enthusiastic about receiving the lessons delivered by the teacher so that they can improve student learning achievement.
2. For future researchers to use other variables that influence student learning achievement. If in the future someone does similar research, they should do it in a different place, add the research variables and adjust the time to the period of the research being carried out.

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